

DYNAMIC LOAD FLOW CALCULATION FOR HEAT TRANSFER NETWORKS

Optimisation of heat transfer networks through realistic mapping of load flows

WHAT BENEFITS DOES DYNAMIC LOAD FLOW CALCULATION OFFER?

Dynamic load flow calculation creates a digital twin of your heat transfer network (HTN). It offers a detailed simulation, including precise temporal and spatial resolution.

This allows you to:

- reduce investment and operating costs
- reduce heat losses
- reduce flow temperatures (if necessary)
- save CO₂ (depending on current supply)

IS THE DYNAMIC LOAD FLOW CALCULATION RELEVANT FOR MY COMPANY?

My company plans to build a new heat transfer network / district heating

OR

operates a heat transfer network / district heating and plans to:

- expand the grid
- optimise the load flows in the grid
- optimise the temperatures
- integrate new heat generation and/or consumption units into the network
- simulate new technologies or use cases (e.g. changed return temperature)

THAT SOUNDS PERFECT! WHAT'S NEXT?

Set up an initial consultation meeting with the NEFI team!

Step 1: Analysis of your heat transfer network / district heating and definition of the scenarios to be analysed

Step 2: Creation of a digital twin of your heat network and simulation of relevant technologies and operating conditions

Step 3: Implementation of the results in the real use case

Our contact details:
office@nefi.at
www.nefi.at/en/
www.vorzeigeregion-energie.at

www.nefi.at/en/solutions